

IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article provides a detailed exploration of modern approaches and tactics for instructing a second language. It also showcases the efficient integration of technologies in teaching English. The author's goal is to emphasize the significance of incorporating up-to-date methodologies in English language education in a comprehensive way.

Keywords: Methods, Project-based learning, innovative teaching, information and communication technology instruction.

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация: В данной статье подробно рассматриваются современные подходы и тактики обучения второму языку. Он также демонстрирует эффективную интеграцию технологий в преподавании английского языка. Цель автора – подчеркнуть важность комплексного внедрения современных методик в обучение английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: Методы, Проектное обучение, инновационное обучение, обучение информационным и коммуникационным технологиям.

INTRODUCTION

Classrooms in modern times are characterized by a wide range of student diversity, encompassing factors such as culture, religion, family background, geographical origins, and previous educational experiences, which is particularly significant in the context of Uzbekistan. This diversity necessitates a shift towards more tailored teaching approaches to accommodate the varied learning requirements of students. In response to these diverse needs, educators at higher education institutions are increasingly employing innovative and differentiated teaching strategies and methods in their classrooms. Over the past thirty years, there has been a global trend towards the adoption of creative teaching techniques to effectively cater to the diverse student population of today. (Barakzai, 2004)

MAIN PART

Improved retention and understanding

Students may lack motivation to learn a certain subject because they fail to recognize its importance, among other reasons. They are far less likely to remember what they are learning as they don't think the material is significant. It is our: teacher's responsibility to demonstrate to them the relevance of the information. There are a number of ways you can do this. For instance, you can use a real-world problem to show students how their lessons can be used to solve the issue. Or, you can get the students to physically or theoretically apply a concept to deal with the world around them. There are many different ways that you can improve learning retention among your students. You simply have to be willing to explore new avenues of teaching. If you do decide to adopt any of the strategies below, you can be certain that you are on the right track. Here are some methods you can use

- Task-based learning
- PBL- project-based learning
- Blended learning
- Collaborative learning
- Jigsaw
- Open-ended questions
- Personalized learning
- Flipped classroom
- Metacognition
- Gamification

Personalized learning experiences

Innovative teaching involves using innovative methods and teaching learning materials for the benefit of students (Mandula, Meda, & Jain, 2012). According to Anderson and Neri (2012), innovative teaching can involve virtual labs: learning activities based on real-life problems; learning environments with equipment, furnishings, materials, and audio-visual resources; and learning guides for students and the teacher. Naturally, using all of the cited materials is not necessary when teaching and studying languages. However, all of these are combined with methodologies that promote the use of active teaching techniques that help teachers develop their students' learning abilities. Teachers across all higher education levels employ a variety of tactics, including personalization, small learning communities, student advisory, multidisciplinary curricula, peer tutoring, peer instruction, and team teaching. Individualization, small learning communities, integrative curricula, student advisories, peer instruction, peer tutoring, team teaching, and so forth are a few examples. Emergent technologies are becoming more and more accessible and capable, which has opened up a wide range of opportunities for creative classroom instruction (Hussain, Niwaz, Zaman, Dahar, & Akhtar, 2010).

Preparation for the future

The new century brought with it significant changes in instruction and teaching methods. The pedagogy of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries are not the same. The evolution of national and global education has undergone numerous changes since the start of the twenty-first century. The Internalization of society and the infiltration of digital technology into education are currently the most noticeable phenomena. Students of today are referred to be digital, socially digital, and generation Z. Knowledge is a move from learning through reading to understanding through visual perception, classroom debate, or the teacher's monologue. (Myamesheva G. 2015). We witness significant developments in informatics and the use of multimedia in the classroom in today's schools. Teachers, sociologists, futurists, and other contemporary scientists talk about a new generation of pupils, or schoolchildren in the twenty-first century. This generation is also known as "Next," "Gen Z," the digital generation, or the social-digital generation (created by L. Hietajärvi and K. Lonka), according to Neil Hove and William Strauss' theory of generations. By incorporating innovative teaching methods in the classroom, teachers can help prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century. Skills such as digital literacy, communication, collaboration, and adaptability are essential in today's globalized world, and innovative teaching methods can help students develop these skills.

Encouragement of critical thinking and creativity

Critical and creative thinking is essential for students to become successful learners not only in the field of language learning but also in some many spheres. **You can help your students develop critical and creative thinking by** encouraging them to explore, be curious, come up with questions and investigate how things work and asking them to describe their thinking and give reasons for it. Innovative teaching methods often require students to think critically, solve problems, and think creatively. This can help develop students' analytical skills, problem-solving abilities, and creativity, which are essential for mastering the English language. Project-based learning (PBL) is an instructional approach that involves students in meaningful, real-world projects to promote learning. It is an approach to student-centered, inquiry-based learning. PBL involves students working in groups for a predetermined amount of time on a project intended to address a difficult subject or solve a real-world problem. Students produce a product or give a presentation for an audience of people to show off their knowledge and abilities. Deep content knowledge can be developed by students through project-based learning activities. Crucially, PBL fosters the growth of 21st century abilities like communication, teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking. PBL can be used in a variety of educational settings, such as high schools and universities.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of innovative teaching methods is indispensable in the field of English language education. By harnessing these methods to enhance student engagement, improve learning outcomes, foster critical thinking and creativity, provide personalized learning experiences, and prepare students for future success, educators can create a dynamic and enriching educational experience that empowers students to excel in both their academic pursuits and beyond.

Literature

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